

Seed Priming Improves Growth and Yield of Moisture-Stressed Rice at Tillering Stage

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Abstract

Moisture stress is among the major banes against production of rice at self-sufficient level. Different growth stages of rice are affected differently by moisture stress. Therefore, we conducted a study to determine the potential of seed priming in alleviating moisture stress in rice at tillering stage. The priming treatments used were 100mM calcium chloride dehydrate, 40% (w/v) polyethylene glycol (PEG)6000 and 100ppm kinetin. Pre-germination which is the farmers' practice was used as the control. We assessed the plants on number of tillers, productive tillers, tillering efficiency and sterility, number of spikelets, filled spikelets, 100 grain weight, grain yield, harvest index, chlorophyll and proline concentration, net photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, inter cellular carbon dioxide and transpiration rate. We found that one day priming with 100ppm kinetin conferred better tolerance against moisture stress and produced higher grain yield than the rest treatments at tillering stage. The outcome of this research is that by using one-day priming with 100ppm kinetin for production of MR219, we can save water at tillering stage and use the saved water for nurturing the plants at booting stage which is ultra-sensitive to water stress.

Keywords: seed priming, moisture stress, growth stages, tillering stage, gas exchange characteristics, rice.

Introduction

The occurrence of water stress for varying intensity and duration could be at different growth stages and such can adversely affect growth, development and yield of plants. When water stress occurs at the vegetative stage, it results in reduction in the number of tillers per hill. This effect seems to be mild compared to imposition of the same stress at reproductive stages. Nevertheless, response to water stress is varietal dependent. This is because some varieties are severely affected at the vegetative stage whereas others are affected at the reproductive stage.

Leaf is the most sensitive organ to environmental stresses (Nevo et al., 2000). Therefore, the effect of water stress is majorly noticed in it more than any other part of the plant. The anatomical

and visual changes found in the leaves during moisture stress period consequently change the diffusion component of carbon dioxide conductance from sub-stomatal area to carboxylation sites and, therefore, contribute to photosynthesis maintenance despite low rate of stomatal conductance (Evans and Loreto, 2000). Mesophyll and stomatal conductance are potentially responsible for reduction in photosynthetic rate when plants are subjected to moisture stress. This implies that the main photosynthetic limitations are diffusional limitations caused by alterations found in the leaf stomata (Loreto et al., 2003)

Chlorophyll which is a light-harvesting pigment in plant is affected by moisture stress. Moreover, changes in chlorophyll *a* and *b* content are noticeable in drought stressed plants (Farooq et al., 2009). Alteration in chlorophyll components and destruction of photosynthetic apparatus and consequent changes in chlorophyll content can reduce net photosynthesis during severe moisture stress (IturbeOrmaetxe et al., 1998). This is because moisture stress decreases chlorophyll contents of the leaves (Ommen et al., 1999). In the same vein, moisture stress results in decrease in chlorophyll *a*,*b* as well as total chlorophyll contents (Manivannan et al., 2007). The reduction in chlorophyll contents could be attributed to damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS) to the chloroplast (Smirnoff, 1995) because drought stress leads to imbalanced production of ROS.

Plants do engage in production of some chemicals (osmolytes) to safeguard them from the destructive effects of moisture stress. Among the produced osmolytes is proline which is believed to be commonly produced by plants under stress like drought, high temperature and starvation (Sairam et al., 2002). Accumulation of proline under moisture stress has been established in pea (Alexieva et al., 2001). Metabolism of proline in relation to osmotic stress has been studied (Verbruggen and Hermans, 2008). Proline accumulation in plants is an indication of environmental stress and could be used as an adaptive response of plants under stress (Maggio et al., 2002).

The challenging problem of moisture stress in rice production calls for a better way out that is simple, effective and adoptable. Among the various strategies that could be used in alleviating moisture stress, seed priming is the physiological approach that is highly effective, with low cost and risk, simple and adoptable (Wahid and Shabbir, 2005). The resulting plants from seed priming could tolerate future stress because their seeds have been subjected to certain degree of stress during priming treatment (Bruce et al., 2007).

The selected treatments from Kareem et al. (2020) which were a two-day osmo-priming and one-day hormonal priming were tested against pre-germination treatment which is the common practice in the granary areas of the country. The objective of this research was, therefore, to determine the potential of seed priming in alleviating moisture stress in rice at tillering stage.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

An experiment to assess the efficacy of rice seed priming in overcoming the problem of incessant water shortage during the subsidiary production season production or unexpected delay in rain to start and maintain rice production on the field was conducted in Rice Research Centre glass house of Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM), Serdang, Selangor, Malaysia (3° 02' N, 101° 42' E; elevation 31 m). The average monthly maximum and minimum temperatures were 33.5 °C and 21.5 °C respectively while the relative humidity is 92.5 %. The sunshine hour is 6.6 h /day while the average rainfall and evaporation are 9.8 mm/day and 4.6 mm/day respectively.

Plant Materials and Experimental Design

The seeds used in this experiment were collected from the gene bank of the faculty of agriculture, UPM. The rice variety researched on was MR219. The priming treatments used were 100mM calcium chloride dehydrate, 40% (w/v) polyethylene glycol (PEG)6000 and 100ppm kinetin. Pre-germination which is the farmers' practice was used as the control. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications.

Agronomic and cultural practices

23kg Kelantan soil series was filled into each of the experimental pot (experimental unit) with diameter 31.5cm and height 36.5cm. The soil was puddled to create an impervious layer which prevents uncontrolled percolation of water and leaching of the nutrient. The water level was then reduced to the barest minimum to pave way for seed-soil-water contact that led to seed germination. Ten seeds were planted per pot. The germinating seeds were irrigated regularly but high level of standing water was prevented to avoid flooding injury. The seedlings were finally reduced to four plants per pot and weed-free till the end of the experiments. The plants were raised under anaerobic condition till the time of stress imposition. After the end of stress period, the initial anaerobic condition was restored and maintained till harvesting.

Stress treatment

At tillering stage (51 days after planting), plants were subjected to a 19-day moisture stress stage). The pots were drained and irrigation was stopped for nineteen days to test their tolerance to water deficit. Irrigation was restored when soil moisture content was 7%.

Data Collection

Plant Phenology and Yield Data

Days to flowering was counted from the time of seeding to the appearance of panicle. Number of filled and unfilled grains or spikelets, weight of 100 seeds, final yield per treatment as well as harvest index were all recorded after harvesting. Harvest index was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Harvest Index} = \frac{\text{weight of Economic yield}}{\text{weight of Biological yield}} \times 100$$

Physiological and Biochemical Data

Determination of leaf chlorophyll content was done following the procedure in Coombs et al. (1985).

Proline Determination

Leaf proline content was estimated colorimetrically using the acid ninhydrin method of Bates et al. (1973).

Determination of Leaf Gas Exchange Characteristics

Data on net photosynthetic rate ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), intercellular carbon dioxide ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2\text{m}^{-1}$), stomatal conductance ($\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) and transpiration rate ($\text{mmol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) were taken with a closed infra-red gas analyzer LICOR 6400 Portable Photosynthesis System (IRGA, Licor Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA) following the procedure of Ibrahim and Jaafar of 2012.

Data Analysis

All the collected data collected in experiments were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) by following RCBD procedure. Significant means were then separated using the least significant difference (LSD).

Results and Discussions

Effect of seed priming on number of tillers of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest number of tillers was recorded from plants resulting from pre-germination followed the plants from calcium chloride priming while plants from kinetin and PEG priming had the lowest number of tillers (Table 1). The vigour gained by pre-germinated seeds was advantageous to the succeeding plants and paved the way for having enhanced number of tillers than the counterpart priming media. Moreover, earliness in the beginning of life of pre-germinated seeds was a strong force necessitating having higher number of tillers than the priming treatments that started pretty late. Furthermore, imposition of stress at tillering stage did not give full time opportunity to the plants from priming treatments to express their full growth potential.

Effect of seed priming on number of productive tillers and tillering efficiency of moisture- stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest number of productive tillers was from plants resulting from kinetin priming followed by plants from calcium chloride priming while the lowest number of productive tillers was from PEG priming (Table 1). The highest percentage of tiller efficiency was from kinetin priming followed by calcium chloride priming while the lowest efficiency was recorded from pre-germination treatment (the control) (Table 1). Productive tillers are pre-requisites for production of higher grain yield provided panicle blanking is prevented through ineffective assimilate partitioning. This performance of kinetin here has given the plants resulting from its treatment to have higher grain yield. Better performance of kinetin priming in tiller productivity was further strengthened by high tiller efficiency and low sterility percentage. Contrary to this, the control as well as the rest priming media had low tiller efficiency and higher sterility percentage.

Table 1. *Effect of seed priming on number of tillers of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage*

Treatments	Number of tillers	Number of Effective Tillers	Tiller Efficiency (%)
CaCl ₂	43.00b	37.00b	77.63b
PEG	42.00b	18.00d	56.24c
Kinetin	42.00b	40.00a	89.11a
Pre-germination	59.00a	32.00c	49.21d

Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different from each other

Effect of seed priming on plant height of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The tallest plants were those from PEG followed by those from kinetin while the shortest ones were those from the control (pre-germination treatment) (Table 2). It could be said that meristematic activities in the plants resulting from priming treatments were more enhanced than that of pre-germination (Werner *et al.*, 2001) since growth division that leads to higher height is the prerogative of the meristematic cells. Moreover, it might still be said that PEG priming aided

physiological activities during plant morphogenesis (Igari et al., 2008). Similarly, absorption of nutrients and water by the roots for better vegetative growth might have been enhanced by the priming chemicals. The degree of enhancement in height was proportional to the level of enhancement in height gain. The superiority of PEG priming still revolves round the fact than its level of stress imposition on the primed seeds during treatment was more than any other priming counterpart. So, when the resulting plants were subjected to real environmental stress similar to the simulated stress by the priming chemicals, the plants thrived with ease the way a vaccinated child scale through of a disease epidemic.

Table 2. *Effect of seed priming on plant height and number of spikelets of moisture- stressed rice at tillering stage*

Treatments	Plant Height(cm)	Number of Spikelets per Panicle
CaCl ₂	86.10b	112.00a
PEG	90.00a	107.00a
Kinetin	87.30b	116.00a
Pre-germination	83.60c	103.00a

Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different from each other

Effect of seed priming on number of spikelets and number of filled spikelets per panicle of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest number of spikelets was from kinetin priming followed by calcium chloride priming while the lowest number of spikelets was from pre-germination (the control) (Table 2). The number of filled grains per panicle did not follow the same pattern as the spikelet production. So, the highest number of filled spikelets was from calcium chloride priming followed by PEG priming while the lowest number of filled spikelets was from kinetin priming (Table 3). This could be attributed to the fact that having large panicle size through increase in number of spikelets will significantly increase the number of poorly filled grains while most of the grains in the inferior spikelets will become source-limited (Kato, 2004). This might be because poor partitioning and translocation of assimilates from the source leaves and stems during grain filling could not sustain the development and filling of a large number of spikelets (Yang et al., 2002). Moreover, starch synthesis in the endosperm cells of inferior spikelets is poor (Umemoto et al., 1994) and assimilates partitioned to them remain unused.

Effect of seed priming on 100-grain mass of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The heaviest seeds were from plants resulting from kinetin and PEG priming followed by pre-germination while the lightest seeds were from calcium chloride priming (Table 3). Increase in grain mass observed in this work with kinetin priming could be attributed to better assimilate partitioning by mitigating the effect of moisture stress. The mass of individual seeds produced from kinetin has contributed to the mass of the final grain yield (Table 3). This could have been the result of better assimilate partitioning though that might have very little or no relationship at all with the light saturated-photosynthesis (Murchie et al., 2002) which might have resulted from the fact that photosynthesis is not affected by antisense which suppresses sucrose transporter gene which impairs rice grain filling (Schofield et al., 2002).

Table 3. Effect of seed priming on number of filled spikelets, 100-grain mass and grain yield of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

Treatments	Number of Filled Spikelets	100-Grain Mass(g)	Grain Yield(g/pot)
CaCl ₂	69.00a	3.63b	46.41a
PEG	65.00a	3.80b	46.12a
Kinetin	60.00a	3.80a	52.44a
Pre-germination	61.00a	3.77b	46.66a

Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different from each other

Effect of seed priming on grain yield of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest yield was from kinetin priming followed by pre-germination treatment while PEG priming produced the lowest grain yield (Table 3). The effect of yield reduction resulting from moisture stress was alleviated through kinetin priming because the treatment produced higher grain yield than the rest priming media including pre-germination treatment which was used as a check because it was the farmers' practice (Table 3). This implies that the effect of moisture stress in grain yield reduction could be alleviated through priming especially hormonal priming like kinetin. This might be because the strength gained through priming with kinetin at vegetative stage mitigated the problems of reduction in grain mass and spikelet fertility which have been identified to be the major sources of yield reduction in rice that is stressed at reproductive stage (Ji et al., 2012). Moreover, it could be that kinetin priming reduced the effect of decrease in assimilate translocation to the reproductive organs of the plant (Hsiao and Xu, 2000) which occurs to rice plant under moisture stress. In the same vein, production of higher grain yield with kinetin priming might have resulted from increase in number of actively reproducing plant cells in inflorescence meristems (Leibfried et al., 2005).

Effect of seed priming on harvest index (HI) of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest value of harvest index was from kinetin priming followed by PEG priming while the lowest value of harvest index was from pre-germination treatment (Table 4). The success of the priming treatments in enhancing effective assimilate partitioning to the filling grains at the reproductive stage might have led to having higher yield and consequently HI. Having higher HI has been established to be the differentiating factor between wild ancestors and cultivated varieties (Gepts, 2004). Environmental factors like temperature (Prasad et al., 2006) and soil conditions which affect the yield are the primary determinants of what the HI will be. Similarly, plant height does affect the HI (Yang and Hwa, 2008) because it determines the plant biomass. Its relationship is indirect and hence, it is not that desired to have too tall plants. The indirect relationship might also be linked to the problem of lodging in tall rice cultivars (Hommaa et al., 2004) which is antithetical to massive assimilate translocation from the vegetative parts to the filling grains in semi-dwarf cultivars (Zou et al., 2003).

Table 4. Effect of seed priming on harvest index (HI), net photosynthesis and stomatal conductance of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

Treatments	Harvest index		
	(%)	Photosynthesis ($\mu\text{molCO}_2\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)	Stomatal conductance ($\text{molH}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)
CaCl ₂	39.71b	0.727b	0.025a
PEG	39.79b	1.504a	0.029a
Kinetin	50.05a	0.139c	0.028a
Pre-germination	22.54c	0.189c	0.017b

Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different from each other

Effect of seed priming on stomatal conductance of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The peak of stomatal conductance was from PEG priming followed by kinetin priming while the lowest was from the control (pre-germination)(Table 4). The maintenance of stomatal opening which kept the conductance at higher rate might have been because priming treatments (PEG and kinetin) did not allow the plants much abscisic acid (ABA) that is responsible for stomatal closure. This is so because the mechanism of stomatal closure during moisture stress is closely linked with ABA because it is amply produced by plants under stress and is, therefore, called stress hormone (Melcher et al., 2009). The mechanism of its operation is that it increases production of cytosolic Ca^{2+} and activates plasma membrane-localized channels (Kohler and Blatt, 2002). Consequently, there is efflux of potassium, depolarization of guard cells, loss of turgor and guard cell volume, high production of hydrogen peroxide and eventual closure of the stomata (Wang et al., 2012).

Effect of seed priming on net photosynthesis of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest photosynthetic rate was recorded in plants from PEG priming followed by calcium chloride priming while the lowest rate was recorded in plants from kinetin priming (Table 4). The highest photosynthetic rate recorded from PEG priming had its root from the stomatal conductance capacity of the resulting plants from PEG priming (Table 4). This implies that stomatal conductance is directly related to photosynthetic rate as it has been established because it is responsible for exchange of gases. This further establishes the relationship between photosynthesis and stomatal conductance (Flexas et al., 2002).

Higher photosynthetic rate through seed priming under moisture stress is an indication of less limitation in both stomatal and non-stomatal (metabolic) factors. The lower values recorded for kinetin priming indicates that there were both stomatal and non-stomatal (metabolic) limitations for decrease in photosynthetic activities. This photosynthetic activity inhibition or decrease found in kinetin priming in this work might result in production of higher level of reactive oxygen which may consequently cause oxidative damage to lipid, proteins, DNA and photosynthetic apparatus (Xiong et al., 2002). This reactive oxygen species causes lipid peroxidation which its extent is measured by malondialdehyde (MDA) content in the tissues (Wang et al., 2014). In the same vein, reduction in photosynthetic rate under moisture stress is the result of its adverse effect electron transport among photosystems I, II and enzymes of carbon metabolism like ribulose-1, 5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco) as well as those enzymes related to its synthesis (Medrano et al., 2002).

Effect of seed priming on intercellular carbon dioxide of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest volume of intercellular carbon dioxide (CO₂) was found in the plants resulting from kinetin priming followed by pre-germination treatment while the lowest concentration was found in the plants from PEG priming (Table 5). Leaves from plants originating from kinetin primed seeds had the highest volume of CO₂ despite the fact that both stomatal conductance and net photosynthesis were at the lowest levels in them. This is a different dimension from the earlier established fact that strong correlation exists between stomatal conductance and inter-cellular CO₂ along with net photosynthesis (Flexas et al., 2002). This result might be because the absorbed CO₂ was judiciously used to leave a significant amount in the intercellular space. This is because the stomatal conductance that should have led to higher accumulation of the gas was low and the photosynthesis that consumes it was lower compared to other treatment (Table 5). Our outcome in this work suggests that the amount of CO₂ does not determine the photosynthetic rate as it is believed that reduction in photosynthetic rate is more influenced by intercellular CO₂ than leaf water potential and leaf water content (Galmes et al., 2011).

Effect of seed priming on transpiration rate of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The best transpiration rate is the lowest under drought stress. Therefore, the best treatment was pre-germination followed by calcium chloride priming while worst treatment was PEG priming (Table 5). The role of pre-germination was also showcased in this experiment because its regulation against water loss was better than the rest of the priming treatments (Table 5). The role of pre-germination in this work is distinct and evident because it had lower transpiration rate. The consequential gain of this phenomenon was realized in the final yield increase as against other priming media with higher transpiration rate and hence more water loss. This conservation of water is attributed to stomatal closure experience at different growth stages when moisture stress was imposed (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of seed priming on intercellular CO₂, transpiration, proline and chlorophyll content of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

Treatment	Intercellular CO ₂ ($\mu\text{molCO}_2\text{m}^{-1}$)	Transpiration rate ($\text{mmolH}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)	Proline Content(μM)	Total Chlorophyll Content (μmolcm^{-2})
CaCl ₂	330.21c	0.97b	30.56c	4.71a
PEG	288.30d	1.34a	33.08b	4.95a
Kinetin	365.67a	1.24a	29.75c	3.98b
Pre-germination	359.00b	0.71b	38.00a	4.01b

Means with the same letters in a column are not significantly different from each other

Effect of seed priming on proline content of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest concentration of proline was found in plants that resulted from pre-germination treatment followed by plants PEG priming while the lowest concentration was found in plants from

kinetin priming (Table 5). It is now clear that stress leads to proline production as found in this work. The concentration found in pre-germination is an indication that pre-germination can also initiate stress tolerance in rice although the physiological intervention did not result in final yield increase. As for kinetin, its ability to produce higher concentration may be an indication of its potential for stress tolerance in rice. Conversely, the mitigation of moisture stress effect did not result in higher grain yield as first noted when stress was imposed. At any instance, it could be inferred that having correct proportion of osmolyte production can only enhance plant tolerance level of the adverse situation and not the grain production directly. This is because accumulation of osmolytes like proline is only an adaptive measure against environmental stresses (Cattivelli et al., 2008).

Effect of seed priming on leaf chlorophyll content of moisture-stressed rice at tillering stage

The highest chlorophyll content was found in leaves of plants from PEG priming followed by calcium chloride priming while the lowest chlorophyll content was found in the leaves of plants from kinetin priming (Table 5). This result might be because PEG priming prevented damage that could be done to the chloroplast by reactive oxygen species which are normally produced as a result of moisture or other environmental stress (Smirnoff 1995). The assertion that high chlorophyll content will result in higher yield (Sengupta and Majumder, 2009) was disproved by PEG priming treatment. Similarly, the observation that higher chlorophyll content is a pre-requisite for high grain yield in rice (Wankhade and Sanz, 2013) was not supported by our result from PEG priming. This might be because chlorophyll level is directly linked to photosynthesis only. So, when the concentration of chlorophyll is high, photosynthetic rate will be high as found in this experiment (Table 4). Nevertheless, photosynthesis has been linked to dry matter yield alone and not the grain yield. But if assimilate partitioning is effective, then photosynthesis will have larger contribution to the grain yield and harvest index will be appreciably high.

Conclusions

From this work, it was found that the priming treatments were better than pre-germination in most of the parameters measured. However, one day priming with 100ppm kinetin was able to tolerate the imposed moisture stress appreciably better than the rest treatments because it led to production of the highest grain yield. It was, therefore, concluded that one day priming with 100ppm kinetin could be used for production of MR219 when there is drought at the tillering stage in the area where the research was conducted and areas with similar climatic and conditions.

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